

TREND OF NUPTIALITY IN THE VILLAGE TEMSKA IN PERIOD 1879-2013

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ABSTRACT: *Marriage structure of the population is one of the basic demographic indicators because of the importance that has for the birth rate and population replacement. In this paper we have analyzed data from the registers of marriages of local offices in the village Temska. Data of the marriage date, place of birth of the spouses, year of birth of the spouses, the data on the distance traveled from the place of birth to the place of marriage, as well as data on the number of divorces were collected. Analyses of these data is the most important part of this paper. The results show that the Temska is in the serious depopulation problem. The constant decline in population automatically caused rapid aging of the population. This is also connected to emigration and most certainly with the decline of the marriage rate. This problem of depopulation is at the beginning so it is necessary to undertake certain measures in order to prevent and stop this negative trend.*

Key words: *Temska, Nuptiality, Pirot, Population*

INTRODUCTION

The settlement, which is the subject of research in this study is located in the municipality of Pirot in eastern Serbia, on the slopes of the Staraplanina mountain. Temska village, throughout history, because of the frequent adverse historical events moved its location downstream and upstream, finally in the nineteenth century because of the bridge that was built over the river Temstic the village was finally situated in the place where it is today. The name of this village comes from the medieval fortress of Tema, which remains are located in the vicinity (Leščešen et al. 2013). A reliable sign of development of a society is the existence of records of its overall history. Investigation of the population age at the time of marriage and nuptiality statistics is of great importance. Since 1895, Serbia has introduced the obligation of civil registration of births, marriag-

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es and deaths. Based on data from the registers of marriages in the period 1879-2013 in Temska village Hajnal division of marital status on the European and non-European model can be tested. According to this division, Serbia is included in the transitional type. No matter which form of marriage exists, it plays a major role in society, because of that that within marriage the largest part of the population reproduction happens (Ivkov, 2007). The research topic is nuptiality of village Temska in the period 1879-2013. Research task is to cover a longer period of time in which in detail can be monitored all of the changes in this phenomenon, to process all the necessary factors which enable us to identify potential causes and foresee the possible consequences. The main goal is to reach concrete results and indicators, to draw attention to the negative effects and point to the measures that would somewhat alleviate this problem.

POPULATION TRENDS

The first data on the population in Temskais given by Felix Kanec in his book “Serbia - the country and the population”, he states that in 1879 Temska had 1035 inhabitants. The first official census, which we had access to was made in 1921, when it Temska lived 2445 inhabitants. The conclusion is that in period of 41 years Temska population grew by 1,410 persons. The next population census was conducted in 1931, points to the trend of population growth with 3,745 inhabitants, which is the maximum number of people in this village in its history (Leščičšen et al, 2013).

Already the next census in 1948, brings the decline in population by 1,501 persons. Such a large population decline is certainly a consequence of the Second World War and the death or exile of a large number of people. From this census year (1948) to the last year covered in this study (2011) steady decrease in the number of inhabitants is clearly shown which is easy to notice in the figure 1. The cause of this negative trend is the reduction of natural growth caused by emigration of fertile population from the village. Most inhabit-

Figure 1. Populations trends in period 1921 - 2011.

Source: Leščičšen et al, 2013

ants 3745 inhabitants, Temska had in 1931, and the lowest number of inhabitants was recorded in last census year (2011) and amounted to 707 persons (Leščešen et al, 2013).

TRENDS IN THE NUMBER OF MARRIAGES

In this village, during the study period a total of 2139 marriages were concluded, or an average of 16.8 marriages per year. Most marriages were concluded in 1947, a total of 70. This phenomenon is easily explained with the end of World War II and the return of young males to the village. The lowest number of marriages were concluded in 1915, 1916, 1998, 2006, 2008 and 2009, only one marriage per year. This information is easily explained by wartime events in that period on one hand, and with a decline in the number of inhabitants in the village in recent years on the other hand. In Figure 2 another minimum of marriages during World War I as well as a double peak that followed him can be seen. Also, after the Second World War, double maximum of slightly higher intensity can be observed. Long wars disrupt the usual life of people. Younger men are in the army, outside their home settlements causing postponement of marriages and child-bearing, and all this is compensated in the post-war years (Ćurčić, 1996).

Figure 2. Trends in the number of marriages in period 1879 - 2013

RATE OF NUPTIALITY

Rate, as a relative number that represents the frequency of an event in a given time interval, is one of the most important indicators of certain events. Marriage rate is directly conditioned by the number of marriages, the greater the number of signed marriage the higher marriage rate will be and vice versa.

Figure 3. Rate of nuptiality in observed period

In Temska during our study period a total of 2139 marriages were concluded, average 16.8 marriages per year. The average rate of marriages is 7.58 ‰. In Figure 3 it can be seen a lot of variation in the marriage rate compared to the average marriage rate. Three periods of low value can be noticed, the first two were recorded during two world wars, and the third period is the period after 1997 and more pronounced emigration primarily of younger population to larger urban centers.

The lowest marriage rate were during the Second World War, 0.83 ‰ followed by a sudden increase and a maximum value of 26.29 ‰ in 1948 and 23.20 ‰ in 1954. These values represent the maximum rate value in this village during the twentieth century. Except for the war years, the lowest value of the marriage rate was recorded in 1998, 1 ‰. After 1956, when the rate of marriages was 20.94 ‰, begins a continuous decline in the marriage rate to the value of 1.33 ‰ in 2009. This data is very worrying because it indicates a steady decrease in the number of marriages in the village which is a consequence of fear of the young people to form a family due to the bad financial situation, but also the acceptance of common-law marriages as new features that occur primarily in developed countries.

THE NUMBER OF MARRIAGES BY MONTH

Analysis of the number of marriages by month provided some very interesting results. It is observed that from the total number of marriages during the whole period (2139), 32.9% were concluded during the winter months (December, January, February), while in the summer period (June, July, August) only 6.6% were concluded.

Based on the Figure 4 it is noticed that the largest number of marriages were concluded in January a total of 685 marriages, because of this it can be marked as the first

Figure 4. The number of marriages by month

maximum month. The second peak occurs in February with total of 392 marriages. The lowest number of marriages were concluded in July, only 4, then in June with 48 marriages. These are two pronounced minimums to which the August with 50 marriages can be added. These differences are explained with the duration of certain holidays during which there are no weddings, and with temperature differences between the two seasons (winter-spring). One of the key reasons is the agricultural works in this rural settlement and preoccupation. The largest number of marriages are concluded during winter. However, interesting is the minimum that occurs during December and which can be explained by the large number of Christian holidays during this month.

THE ISONYMY

The indicators of the isonymic marriages represents the same surnames of the bride and groom at the wedding. In investigation period in Temska18 cases were recorded. Most oftensurnames are following: Djordjevic (three times), Jovanovic (twice), while the surnames Rancic, Zirić, Petrovic, Krstic, Petkovic, Veljkovic, Vasic, Vidakovic, Pasic, stripling, Colic, Antic and Lazarevic appeared only once.

Such marriages with the same last name may be explained by the decision of the family to marry distinct relatives to preserve the property, as well with that the woman previously was married to a cousin of the current husband chosen and kept his surname, or it is the same name of different origins which is explained with coincidence.

MEDIAN AGE AT FIRST MARRIAGE

Median age of men in the period 1879 - 2013 is 22 years and women for 21, the difference is between spouses is only one year. By the end of the Second World War, the median age of spouses range mostly below average, 16.7 years for grooms and brides 17.2 years. On average, the groom were youngest in 1896 and 1913 (19.7 and 19.3 years old), while brides were the youngest in 1904 and 1928 (18.5 years). After World War II the mean age of the spouse is growing, and moving slightly above the average for the whole observed period. The median age of the groom after the Second World War was 26 years old and brides 23.9 years. Grooms have on average the youngest in 1966 (22 years), and brides in 1965 (16.8 years). It is noted that the increase in the mean age occurs in both men and women, as we approach the end of the research period.

With existing data of average age of groom and bride in the period 1879 - 2013, it was possible to determine the maximum age values. The highest average age of groom was recorded in 2008, with 66 years, and the brides were the oldest in 2008, 69 years. However, it should be noted that this year, and the following 2009, only one marriage per year was concluded per year, and both spouses were over 60 years old. Excluding these two years, we come to the new data with the highest average age of grooms was recorded in 2001 with 49.7 and brides in 2000 to 52.5 years.

The highest average age difference between spouses was recorded in 2000, 26.5 years, in contrast, the smallest difference was recorded in 1894, 1895, 1902, 1911, 1927 and 1933 and amounted to 0.1 year, while never a mean age of groom and bride was the same. The median age of the spouse at the time of their first marriage in Temska village tends to increase (based on available data, it was not possible to separate the marriage first and higher order).

Figure 5. The rate of the median age at first marriage between spouses in period 1879-2013

Serbia is located east of the line Trieste-St Petersburg, and according to the territorial division it belongs to the Eastern European transition model according to Hajnal, who are characterized by the following characteristics:

- Women should marry between the ages of 20-23 years and men by 27.
- By the age of 50 marriages should be concluded between 90 to 95% of population (Đurđev, 1991)

Analyzing data presented on the Figure 4 it can be seen that the average age of both women and men, in the period 1901-1945, have values that belong to the Eastern European transition, where they belong on the territorial position. We note that the average age of the bride is 21, and the average age of the groom is 22, both below the threshold. The period after World War II, the mean age of the bride and groom has the characteristics of the Western European model of marital status. Period 1946-2013 was marked by an increase in average age of newlyweds, especially at the end of the period under review.

If we compare the movement of average age of women and men during the marriage can be seen that they have a very similar tendencies of movement, with fluctuations, rises or falls in the same years. Late marriages in recent years can be explained by the way of thinking of modern girls, their higher level of education, and poor material conditions because of which the young people are deciding for later marriages.

THE AGE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN SPOUSES

Based on our research, the age difference between spouses in the village Temska during the period 1897-2013 on average was 2.7 years. There is a negligible number of marriages in which the woman is older, and marriages where the spouses are of the same age. Such phenomena occur mainly during the war times. It is noticeable that the age differ-

Figure 6. Medium age difference between spouses in period 1879-2013

ence is the same, which occurs as a result of the same cultural circle and historical development to which spouses belong.

In Figure 6 it can be seen that the average difference between the newlyweds mostly ranges between 1 to 10 years. Minimum age difference between spouses is recorded in following years: 1894, 1895, 1902, 1911, 1927 and 1933 (0.1) while the highest difference was registered in the end of the period, 1997 (12.4).

HOMOGENITY OF MARRIAGES

According to the place of birth, the spouses, according to LePage classification, classified into 4 groups:

- SS - both spouses born in the place where the marriage was concluded
- SM - the groom was born in the place where the marriage was concluded and a bride in the other place
- MS - the bride was born in the place where the marriage was concluded and groom in the place
- MM - both spouses born out of places where they got married

Information's about the homogeneity of marriages are used to calculate the homogeneity index which represents the ratio of marriages between spouses who were born in the place where the marriage took place and of marriages between spouses, whose birth-place is outside the place where they got married. The value of this index can be in the range of -1 to 1. As the value is closer to 1 the population is less open (endogenous population) and in the opposite case, when it is closer to -1 it is the open population (exogenous population).

Figure 7. Difference between the origin of the spouses in period 1920 – 2009

Figure 8. Index of homogamy in period 1920 – 2009

In Figure 7, we have vision in relation to the origin of the spouses. We note that 61% of spouses, whether male or female, originally from Temska. The other part, 39% is from the surrounding settlements, primarily from Rudinje, Ragodeš, Sopot, Oreovica etc.

Analyzing the data presented in the figure 8 we can conclude that the population during the period, although the index value ranging mostly from 0 to 0.3, was mostly closed, endogenous to the values closest to 1. Population was mainly the closed on the beginning of the period until the beginning of World War II, in 1942. After this period, we note two negative values that the population makes exogenous. This period can be called the first negative fluctuations in the index of homogamy. Another two periods are of major proportions. The first was from 1973 to 1976 with values of -0.016 to -0.64. Second, the greatest period was from 1981. to 1984. However, this negative ranking was stopped by value of 0.4, which was recorded in 1985. After 1984, the population takes on endogenous characteristics that were held with minor oscillations by the end of the period under review. We should also mention the period between 1998-2009 when the value of the index amounted to 0, which indicates a little more open population. During this period stands out 2003 with a value of -0.33, which disrupts this series.

MARITAL DISTANCE

Marital distance is the distance in kilometers by the parties proceed from the birthplace of the place where the marriage is concluded.

Table 1. The numerical value of the age of the bride and groom to their origin

Birthplaces	Number of spouses
Temska	1574
Rudinje	510
Ragodeš	184
Sopot	49
Oreovica	37
Cerova	35
Staničenje	30
Čuštica	29
Pirot	19
Bazovik	15
Mirkovci	14
Topli Do	13
Zaskovci	12
Crvenčevo	10
Crnoklište	9
Zavoj	8
Koprivštica	7
Pokrevenik	7
Nišor	6
Dobri Do	6
Beograd	9
Osmakova	4
Sinjac	3
Orlja	3
Zaječar	3
Bor	2
Niš	2

Settlements are listed by given the newlyweds. This table presents number of newlyweds from individual settlements for the period from 1920 to 2009. Most of the newlyweds came from surrounding towns, villages, which are also the closest village Temska. On the map showing the marital distance, one can see that the number of newlyweds

Figure 9. Marital distance in the reporting period

decreases with the distance of the village. What is interesting is that we see the arrival of the newlyweds from remote areas and towns such as Obrenovac, Belgrade and from cities outside the borders of our country, Maribor and Ljubljana. Such marriages are relatively small, mostly assembled at a marriage.

The graph shows the marital distance for villages from which there has been at least 15 spouses that came in Temska in order to get married. Each concentric circle in this view of marital distance represents the distance of the villages in kilometers. Each circle represents the distance from Temska which is higher than the last 10km. Most newcomers newlyweds came from the nearest villages, Rudinje, Ragodeš, Sopot, Oreovica etc. The total distance that the couples made to the place of marriage is 12 731km, men have crossed the 4 401km and women 8 330km.

Looking at the population trends of the 1920s until today, the number of newcomers newlyweds is reduced as a consequence of poor living in the countryside as well as the growing phenomenon of conurbation and the departure of young people to the cities in order to find a better place to live and find a job.

CONCLUSION

Data on the characteristics of marriages in the period 1979-2013 in the village of Temska indicate that on the beginning of the century nuptiality was almost universal, and age at first marriage was low. During the period age at first marriage has increased. The age difference between spouses is on average 2.7 years and did not reveal any regularity. Homogamy indices are mostly closed, endogenous type with the values closest to 1. Although the allocated periods where these series are terminated. From the calculation of the marital distance, we note that more mileage to the place of marriage crossed bride. Newlyweds are the most from Temska, Rudinje and Ragodeš, after which there are Sopot, Oreovica and Cerova.

Based on the presented results we can conclude that in this village there is a serious problem of its aging and gradual extinction. It can be concluded from the constant decline in population, expressed emigrations primarily young population, but certainly the reduction of nuptiality. Although the trend of depopulation is in its initial phase, it is necessary to begin to implement some of the measures that could be taken to prevent this negative demographic trend in which the cause is, above all, the departure of young people. It is necessary that young people are provided to the better living conditions in order to decide to stay on the family farms, that in this village marry and to found a family. It is necessary to provide the conditions that would lead to the fact that they have more than one child, in order to rejuvenate this village again and eventually survive.

While Haynal division of marital status, that is used in the paper, can be generally used for research, transversal and longitudinal analysis of the basic components of nuptiality can not fully confirm this Haynal's typology.

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